

Management Efficacy in the Delivery of Quality Education in Deped Secondary Schools

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Abstract:- The research assessed the management practices of the school administrators and faculty members of the five identified secondary schools in the Medellin District, namely: Kawit National High School, Medellin National High School, Medellin National Science & Technology School, Curva National High School, and Almacen - Torrevillas National High School, especially in the new educational setting with their chosen learning modality implemented in their institution brought by COVID19 crisis School Year 2020 - 2021 as the basis for continuous development programs. The study employed the descriptive normative survey method utilizing the questionnaire technique resorting to the complete enumeration among the one hundred seventy-three (173) respondents in the High School in terms of; personal background as regards: age, gender, civil status, combined monthly income, and professional qualification in terms of degree earned, major and or minor field of specialization, length of teaching experience, latest performance rating, the levels of manifestation and the external and internal factors affecting management practices. Results showed that only external and internal factors had a significant relationship involving the implementation of management practices of the respondents in which the *p-value* was 0.008, which was lesser than 0the .05 level of significance. After the conduct of this study, an indicated conclusion, most notably on the external and internal management practices, the formulated continuous development programs must be strictly implemented. Therefore, this study also offered recommendations that could contribute significantly to their success as an educator, administrators, and an individual.

Keywords:- Development Education; Management Practices; Descriptive -Correlational Method; Medellin, Cebu Philippines.

I. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Many of the public and private sectors are affected by these global health crises nowadays. It is the occurrence of the newly detected virus that struck worldwide. The novel human coronavirus disease, or COVID-19 has become the fifth documented pandemic since the 1918 flu pandemic. The first case of COVID-19 was in Wuhan, China, and subsequently spread worldwide. Aspects of life are affected, namely: physical, moral, spiritual, and emotional. Public and

private agencies are closed to prevent the virus's rampant spreading, and total lockdowns are implemented and felt in every community and other establishments.

Education is also one of the agencies that are greatly affected by the threat of this pandemic. The opening of classes was canceled how many times, there was no face-to-face delivery of quality instruction, and most of all, safety protocols by the IATF must be strictly followed. According to Education for All (EFA) mandates, schools are obliged to support and provide interventions for effective learning to happen continuously. Different learning modalities are created and, at the same time, implemented by the education committees. Education is a human right throughout life (UNESCO). This access must be matched with quality. It transforms lives and is at the heart of UNESCO's mission to build peace, eradicate poverty and drive sustainable development (<https://en.unesco.org/themes/education>). It is where we fill up our empty minds with relevant prior knowledge to upgrade mental capacities and skills and be the torch of hope and wisdom to the young generation. But one thing has changed in the context of education: the management practices of teachers in this new educational setup, both small and large school categories, on how they handle such field works in these trying times. According to Harold Koontz (1909 - 1984), a famous American management theorist, "Management is an art and style of accomplishing things through and with the people in formally organized groups". It also refers to the coordination and administration of tasks to attain the desired outcome. It helps achieve group goals, utilizes resources, reduces costs, establishes sound organization and equilibrium, and is essential for the prosperity of society (https://www.managementstudyguide.com/management_importance). In life, Management plays a vital role in attaining such objectives and aspirations. It is substantial, and it will lead to a smooth and orderly manner of work. Further, Forsyth (2010) suggested that keeping a work-life balance necessitates efficiently and effectively managing the limited resources and available time.

However, in educational practice, teachers' classroom management practices directly impact students' success. The overall purpose of management practices in education is to effectively and efficiently create and maintain environments within and other educational institutions that promote, support, and sustain effective teaching and learning. Teaching must subject itself to organized and objective planning,

preparation, and execution of the lessons to direct the learners towards the different learning episodes (Lualhati, 2019).

Teachers find it very convenient as the momentum of their duties and responsibilities remain smooth and coherent if these management practices are wholeheartedly followed despite the pandemic or any uncontrolled disturbances. It also requires effective time management, for it increases an individual's confidence and makes him self-assured. Fleming (2011) said that individuals who can accomplish tasks within the stipulated time frame could improve their lives and be balanced not only in their organization but also amongst their peers and family. Furthermore, much of their time, money, and effort will be saved if good Management is given importance and carried out to the whole system of every responsible citizen of the country. Nowadays, in the Philippine educational system, there is an innovation called School-Based Management (SBM) under Republic Act No. 9155, also known as "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001". Other legal bases include School First Initiative (SFI, 2005) and Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA, 2006). It is a management framework that is school-based, student-centered, and quality-focused. It provides the overall framework for principal-teacher empowerment by strengthening principal-teacher leadership and management goals, specifically local school-based Management, within transparency and local accountability. Lastly, the School-Based Management (SBM) will help give better service and quality management to humanity, particularly learners, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders, as part of DepEd's mission and vision. But how can a teacher manage his or herself, time, and efforts among all barriers or challenges in delivering quality instruction in this new educational setup, and what are his or her management practices in achieving his or her goals?

The problem, as mentioned above, remains significant in both rural and urban schools. Thus, it is a long line of thought that the researcher picks up on this problem to determine factors affecting internal and external management practices of teachers and their relevance to 21st-century skills development in the new educational setting due to the threat of this pandemic, specifically the five secondary schools of Medellin District, the School Year 2020 - 2021 and to identify continuous development program to promote effective and efficient teaching and learning.

❖ *Statement of the Problem*

The research ascertained the management practices of school administrators and teachers in the delivery of quality instruction in DepEd secondary schools in the new educational setup, particularly five identified public high schools of Medellin District school year 2020 - 2021, as the basis for continuous development programs.

To have a clearer insight into the subject under study, the following inquiries were formulated.

- What is the profile of the school administrators and teachers, in terms of:

- personal background, as to:
 - ✓ age;
 - ✓ gender;
 - ✓ civil status; and
 - ✓ combined family income?
- professional qualification, as to:
 - ✓ degree earned;
 - ✓ major/minor field of specialization;
 - ✓ length of teaching experience; and
 - ✓ latest performance rating?

- What is the level of manifestation of the management practices as perceived by the school leaders and teachers in terms of:

- leadership;
- curriculum and instruction;
- learning environment;
- finance and resource management mobilization;
- governance; and
- human resource and team development?

- What are the factors affecting the management practices of school leaders and teachers in the new normal in terms of:

- external factors, as to:
 - ✓ distance of home from school;
 - ✓ mode of transportation;
 - ✓ time of travel;
 - ✓ time to transfer from one house to another during distribution;
 - ✓ reasons of home tutors when not around;
 - ✓ challenges met by the Teacher outside school; and
 - ✓ time of sleep?
- internal factors, as:
 - ✓ schedule in giving/distributing modules;
 - ✓ reasons why late in giving/distributing modules;
 - ✓ time management;
 - ✓ how they spend their free time; and
 - ✓ challenges met by the Teacher in school?

- Is there a significant relationship between age, gender, combined family income, and the factors affecting the implementation of management practices of school administrators and teachers in the new normal?

- Is there a significant relationship between the external factors and the internal factors affecting the implementation of management practices in delivering quality instruction to students by the school administrators and teachers?

- Is there a significant relationship between the levels of manifestation and the external and internal factors affecting the management practices of teachers in the new educational setup?

- Based on the findings, what continuous development programs can be generated to eliminate hindrances in the implementation of management practices of teachers despite the pandemic in the five secondary schools of Medellin District?

❖ *Null Hypotheses*

Based on the problem, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

H₀: There is **no** significant relationship between age, gender, combined family income, and the factors affecting the implementation of management practices of the school administrators and teachers in the new normal.

H₀: There is **no** significant relationship between the external factors and the internal factors affecting the implementation of management practices.

H₀: No significant relationship between the levels of manifestation and the external and internal factors affecting the management practices of school administrators and teachers in the new educational setup.

II. RELATED LITERATURE

The novel human coronavirus disease, or COVID-19, has become the fifth documented pandemic since the 1918 flu pandemic. This global threat has fundamentally affected nearly every area of life, including education, and our country has not been an exception.

The first reported COVID-19 case was in Wuhan, mainland China, and subsequently spread worldwide. The coronavirus was named severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses based on phylogenetic analysis. SARS-CoV-2 is believed to be a spillover of an animal coronavirus and later adapted the ability of human-to-human transmission (Y. Chen, Q. Liu, and D. Guo, 2020). It is highly contagious, and the virus rapidly spreads and continuously evolves in human transmission. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the most appropriate way to prevent and stem the transmission is to be aware of the COVID-19 virus, the disease it causes, and how it spreads. Protecting ourselves from infection is done by washing hands, using an alcohol-based rub frequently, and not touching one's face.

Public and private sectors or organizations across the country share a significant dilemma of struggling with the pandemic threat. Total lockdowns affected stores, schools, and other establishments within the community. Guidelines and other stringent measures were fully implemented by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It significantly affects the economy and has a domino effect on one and all. There was the slashing of staff or workers and, at the same time, the sudden increase in unemployment rate and hunger during this recurring and severe problem that we're facing.

In the context of education, UNESCO has observed that most world governments have temporarily shut down the educational institutions to contain the COVID-19 pandemic. These nationwide closures were impacting over 60% of the world's student population. Education specialists were having a difficult time opening classes without increasing the rate of COVID19 cases. In the country, Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) heads discuss possible interventions in continuing the mandates of Education for All (EFA) and introduce new

learning modalities. These learning modalities include Modular Distance Learning, Online Distance Learning, and Television/Radio-Based Instruction. It's up to the school on what learning modality fits the needs, location, availability of gadgets, capacity of their students, and parents' socioeconomic status.

The Teacher, who is considered the second mother of a student, was having a tough time addressing the new normal. Teachers had a hard time preparing instructional materials to deliver quality and excellent instruction to meet the demands of the learning modality chosen by the school. Teachers experience too much stress and burnout while sailing amid the pandemic. Furthermore, the stress has a great representation to public secondary education level school teachers. According to the study, one of the primary reasons for teachers' stress is time and concern for students. Many educators feel morally responsible for their student's well-being (Nyambongi, 2014).

With this, Management is vital and is the main point of the study. According to Henri Fayol (1841-1925), a famous management theorist, defined Management as the process of forecasting and planning, organizing, leading, coordinating, and controlling the resources of an organization in the efficient and effective pursuit of a specified organizational goal. It has four standard functions: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling (McDonald, 2010). Leung and Kleiner (2004) recommend that these four functions are vital but insufficient in implementing successful Management, with strong significance placed on adopting practices that focus on employees within organizations.

In lieu of educational Management, Babalola (2006), believed that this is a concept that goes with the journey to put the formal education system under control, regulation and supervision. Idoko (2015) also viewed that Management as the process, will help through educational institutions for the development of human personality. Thus, the major duty of the manager in an educational institution is to get the work done in order to accomplish the objectives as pre-planned.

Management practices are the working methods and innovations used to have a smooth workflow to accomplish a desired goal or outcome. It is considered the most satisfying career a professional could make.

To some management authors, they define management practices as an entity of analytical instruments used to support the managers at work as something used in the implementation of the selected management concept (Dessler, 2004; Sutherland & Canwell, 2004; Van Assen et al., 2009). Another definition proposed by Rigby (2001) considers management practices as tools defined as a set of concepts, processes, and exercises.

In the contemporary business environment and practice, organizations use various management practices to support their operations. Within that framework, management practices represent an essential factor that has a necessary

impact on operations of and work in organizations, and consequently underpin the competitiveness of an organization (Sutherland & Canwell, 2004; Van Assen et al., 2009; Potočan & Dabić, 2012; Dabić et al., 2013; Nedelko & Potočan, 2013). Moreover, organizations use different management practices at different developmental levels of their business and in other business environments - e.g., well-developed, catching-up economies. The use of good management practices has a vital role in catching-up economies, which try to reduce their developmental lag, reduce inequality and increase their competitiveness in comparison to the more developed economies (Dyck & Mulej, 1998; Newman, 2000; Kaplan & Norton, 2008; Kozminski, 2008; Nedelko & Potočan, 2013).

However, the value of Management was diminishing, especially in the field of education. Teachers planned and prepared modules and executed lessons through home visits and virtual applications to direct the learners towards the different learning episodes. It often robbed another opportunity to teachers and dispatched forces nowadays, especially in this new educational setup. School Heads and Teachers met some barriers that hinder the implementation of management practices, both external and internal aspects. For external elements; the challenges include; distant houses of students for the reason that they usually live in mountainous or in far-flung areas; parents did not value education because some of the students belong to the DDU sector (depressed, deprived, and underserved) and other teachers don't have transportation in delivering modules. Internal factors include loaded paper works, overload of subjects of teachers, huge schools with more students or population, poor internet connection, many unanswered or unsubmitted modules, and most of all when the school head conducts an emergency meeting.

Over the past decades, education systems worldwide have evolved from large centralized structures to more decentralized ones. It has become the general trend in school management. It gave rise to the Department of Education's (DepEd) intervention, the School-Based Management Practices (SBM) under DepEd Order 83, s. 2012, used in public and private schools. SBM is a management framework that is school-based, student-centered, and quality-focused. It also provides principals, teachers, students, and parents greater hold over the education process by providing them authority for decisions about the budget, personnel, and curriculum and will focus efforts on strengthening the support systems of the DepEd through improved educational planning and Management. Due to the involvement of teachers, parents, and other community stakeholders in these key decisions, SBM can formulate more effective learning environments for children. (<https://www2.ed.gov/pubs/OR/ConsumerGuides/baseman.html>). It is a good strategy to improve education by transferring significant decision-making with good school management practices.

Republic Act 9155 (RA 9155), otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, hereby declared the state's policy to protect and promote the right of all

Filipino citizens to quality primary education and make such education accessible to all. It also stated the framework for principal empowerment by strengthening principal and leadership goals and local school-based Management in transparency and local accountability. Moreover, as indicated in RULE VI, the school head shall be the instructional leader and administrative manager to lead and manage educational policies, plans, and standards, thereby having the authority, responsibility, and accountability to achieve higher learning outcomes. It is also shared governance between the school administrators and teachers to support the stewardship of children's learning outcomes, and it is both a process and a product.

The teaching profession is highly inspiring, intellectually demanding, and emotionally rewarding, according to Lualhati (2019). It requires a suitable arrangement of specific procedures and timelines along with good intent and self-awareness. Brott (2008) said being more productive, having more energy to accomplish tasks, feeling less stressed, possibly pursuing personal, getting more things done, relating to others more positively, and feeling better about self are the effects of good time management practices.

However, it still needs an organization of management practices through continuous development planning to help schools promote a well-managed environment and produce effective and efficient teachers during the pandemic. The use of management practices was recognized as an essential driver of competitiveness and growth (Potočan & Dabić, 2012; Potočan et al., 2012; Dabić et al., 2013; Nedelko & Potočan, 2013) and therefore considered an essential factor that supports the improvements of organizations and even schools. In addition, a great manager and a leader are someone who can motivate their team and follow school management best practices for success. Thus, teachers supported by effective Management and leadership were widely held as keys to education quality and change (Chapman & Adams 2002).

III. RELATED STUDIES

Teachers, administrators, and school officials have a significant role in upholding one of the child's rights, which is the right to education. They work hand in hand to make it accessible and feasible to all. School leaders, both teaching and non-teaching personnel create the culture and organization for schools to give quality teaching and have an indirect but essential effect on student learning (OECD, 2016; UNESCO, 2018; World Bank, 2018). Teachers are best considered one of the most influential and powerful enablers for educational equity and quality to achieve sustainable global development (<https://en.unesco.org/themes/teachers>). Teachers who are new to distance learning may feel unprepared to facilitate teaching, thus needing technical, pedagogical, and time management (Dyment, 2013). Like every other sector, the education landscape has been wholly impacted in all nations and at all levels of academic institutions, as the ingenuity of educators has been forcibly stretched as a coping mechanism in the face of crisis, Kaur, N. (2020). The forced closure of schools and universities as a

result of the COVID-19 pandemic has presented an opportunity for disruptive innovation to take shape in the field of education. However, given that the pandemic spread so swiftly worldwide these left institutions scrambling to move all courses fully online in a matter of days. Unfortunately, most schools and universities did not have in place a robust business continuity plan and lacked the considerable resources needed to develop good online courses rapidly. Hence, this will likely lead to adverse reactions from students and teachers alike to the poor transition to and implementation of online learning, consequently causing an acceptance of virtual learning as lukewarm if the initial implementation is not executed satisfactorily (Lederman, 2020). This has become the major problem of the teachers who are in public schools since most of the students do not have the resources to do online classes. Thus, the Department of Education implemented the Basic Education Learning Continuity plan to continue delivering the lessons to the students. Through the varied challenges set by the Department of Education, teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders carried too much weight in terms of workloads as to how they juggle both compliance and in delivering students' lessons through a modular learning approach. In a nutshell, a perusal of the studies revealed that a large number of researches had been utilized on blended learning, but no study talks about the readiness of the teachers themselves. Teachers are suddenly told to adapt to this new educational form of teaching due to the threats of the virus. Most educational institutions had to shut down and face to face orientation of teachers on e-learning has not been conducted and regulated. In addition, most of the institutions were unable to provide any technical assistance to their teachers. Thus, considers these parameters to understand the readiness of teachers to adapt to blended forms of learning. Parameters like gender, hands-on experience to learn and teach online, and the highest qualification of the teachers make a difference in the attitude of the Teacher to adapt to the blended form of learning.

The Teacher is committed to enduring all the teaching responsibilities along with more time filling out paper works, grading schoolwork, dealing with administrators, handling learners at risk of dropping out, and attending meetings against all odds (Lualhati, 2019). Teachers encounter difficulties in paperwork submission and task accomplishments. According to Teacher no. 2; "*Kapag nagkasabay-sabay ang napakaraming paperworks at deadlines pero at the same time ay kailangan pa ring magturo.*" Almost 9 of 10 teachers feel stressed and anxious caused by the pandemic. Additionally, the survey report revealed that 81% of the educators who were respondents to the study are setting in more than 14 hours a day to accomplish their professional responsibilities (Schaffhauser, 2020).

Moreover, tasks such as the students' grades also brought difficulties to them, especially in the time of the pandemic where communication was limited and challenged. Moreover, it is getting harder for them to guide the students' outputs given to them. Certainly, Teacher no. 3 said that; "*Ngayon talaga nahihirapan ako sa paghagilap ng mga mag-*

aaral sa hindi paggawa at pagpasa ng module." Problems were already evident at school; however, studying at the pandemic was not different; in fact, it was worse, according to the participants. The lack of necessary equipment in the public school systems brought hardship to the school's key indicators, specifically, teachers and students. According to the aforementioned, the Philippine teachers are adamantly stressed because budget constraints. The study further revealed that teachers are in a state of distress, looking for possible ways to make sure that their local governments' given account would meet all of their students' needs (Granthorn, 2020).

Due to these overwhelming tasks, most teachers file for indefinite sick leave, which is already struggling with recruitment and retention. In fact, according to Ansis (2017), based on CNN-Philippines, one of the most stressful jobs in the country is teaching. Teachers, therefore, shall have time management practices along with scheduling, goal setting, prioritizing tasks, doing paperwork, handling interruptions, and challenges that they meet every day in managing their time, especially in these trying times. Teaching must subject itself to organized and objective planning, preparation, and execution of the lessons to lead the learners into the different learning episodes every quarter or semester. Moreover, educators serve many roles, and they are expansive from imparting knowledge to safeguarding children's welfare, inspiring critical thoughts, and sharing moral values (<https://www.totaljobs.com/advice/teacher-job-description>). Therefore, they are very passionate and dedicated individuals with a strong desire for developing lifelong learning for learners.

Some educational institutions implement policies particularly for teachers to manage their time and efforts, especially in the pandemic, to provide a supportive learning environment. In addition, they shall make sure that policies and Management practices have exceptions and seek feedback from students and parents as home tutors to fulfill their absolute potential (Villanueva, 2018). Consequently, a teacher who can manage their time well implies a well-managed class, whatever learning modality they choose. Numerous countries of the world have introduced the aspect of decentralization of educational Management. It means that the Management of education that the government traditionally provided has changed, and is currently under the school administrators' and directors' responsibilities. A pilot study conducted in the year 2008 in Kenya showed that many countries that launch education decentralization and the delegation of management and leadership duties have insufficient knowledge and skills regarding the sub-national units' readiness. In line with this, educational Management and school improvement should not be taken for granted as they significantly impact the students' quality of education (Harris et al., 2004, p. 78). Due to this study, Kenya's ministry of education (MoE) decided to design a professional development program, especially for local education authorities, to build up skills and experiences lacking in this sector.

The educational Management's decentralization is the aspect of entrusting some duties and responsibilities to local school administrators and managers because they are closer to students and parents (Hopkins, 2001, p. 38). It may be challenging for a government to manage all the activities performed in a school or provide adequate and high-quality education. In the current agitating marketplace, it is essential to understand the fundamental connections between society, environment, and business (Hopkins, 2005, p. 18). In this case, this increased interdependence and complexity usually require new approaches to be employed in an organization's leadership and management practices. Educational institutions, therefore, need integrative management tools that integrate societal, environmental, and governance concerns into their strategic thinking (Hoy & DiPaola, 2009, p. 56). School administrators ensure students' capabilities to be future generators of sustainable value for society and business (Huisman & Pausits, 2010, p. 7). It shows that education management is not solely in the hands of school administrators, but parents, teachers, and students are involved in coming up with effective educational management procedures (Kangro, 2007, p. 27).

Moreover, the Teacher can also keep up with the educational needs of every student, manage pressing situations immediately, and avoid failing when unexpected situations arise. Cottrell (2013) defines time management as a combination of social life, employment, family, and personal interests and commitments with the finiteness of time. Thus, it is the utmost intention of the researcher to strengthen their management practices despite the COVID19 crisis, which will help them become more effective and efficient professionals or individuals and give further recommendations that may contribute significantly to one's success as an educator and the bearer of hope of the fatherland.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This was quantitative research utilizing the descriptive-normative survey method using a modified questionnaire on management practices. This primarily sought to find out the prevalent factors affecting the implementation of management practices of administrators and teachers of the school in the new normal of the identified five public secondary schools of Medellin District, the School Year 2020 - 2021. The study employed a universal sampling or complete enumeration among the one hundred seventy-three (173) teachers, including school administrators of the five secondary schools of Medellin District, on the factors affecting the implementation of management practices, both external and internal aspects in the new educational setup or platform implemented and its relevance to 21st-century skills development. The study centered on school administrators and teachers' management practices in the new normal setup of education in the Municipality of Medellin, particularly five public secondary schools school year 2020 - 2021. The researcher used the descriptive-questionnaire technique in the gathering of data. The gathered data were then treated using the simple percentage formula, Weighted Mean, Coefficient of contingency, Pearson r, and T-test. The

outcomes of the study were used as the basis for providing some continuous improvement/development programs to provide quality instruction despite the global crisis brought by COVID19.

V. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

The study ascertained the management practices of school administrators and teachers in delivering quality education in DepEd secondary schools in the new educational setup, particularly five identified public high schools of Medellin District school year 2020 - 2021 as the basis for continuous development programs.

The descriptive-normative survey method was utilized during the conduct of the survey. The analysis of data was done with a complete universal sampling method of five (5) identified secondary schools of Medellin District with a total of one hundred seventy-three (173) respondents, comprising six (6) school heads and one hundred sixty-seven (167) teachers, of which the data were subjected to the percentage and the average weighted mean. It primarily sought to determine the prevalent factors affecting management practices in the new educational setup of the five high schools as the participating environment in the Municipality of Medellin, School Year 2020 - 2021.

➤ *Profile of the Respondents: The School Administrators and The Teachers*

School Administrators. Consequently, the profile of the school heads could be summarized in two sub aspects: the personal and professional backgrounds.

In the **personal background**, specifically on **gender**, only 1 or 16.67 percent were male, and 5 or 83.33 percent were females. All of them had an **age** of 56 and above. Regarding **civil status**, 4 or 66.66 percent were married, followed by single and the widow with 1 or 16.67 percent. They also had a **combined monthly income** of 40, 001 – 50, 000 since their Salary Grades were 19 for Assistant Principal and Principal 1 and 20 for Principal 2, respectively. As to the **type of learning modality implemented in school**, 6 or 100 percent of them had chosen modular print for it's the only modality applicable to students, mainly those who belonged to the DDU sector (depressed, deprived, and underserved) and lived in far-flung or mountainous barangays.

On **professional qualification**, as to **degree earned**, 4 or 66.67 percent were bachelor's degree holders with master's units, and 2 or 33.33 percent were master's degree holders. As to the **major and or minor field of specialization**, 3 or 50 percent of school principals were English majors, Social Studies majors with 2 or 33 percent, and 1 or 17 percent were Physical Science/Biological Science Major. Regarding the **length of teaching experience**, 6 or 100 percent of them had rendered 21 years and above in public service, with the **latest performance rating** of Very Satisfactory (VS), which ranged from 3.500 – 4.499.

Teachers. The Junior High and Senior High Teachers' profile was also categorized into two sub-aspects: personal and professional qualifications.

For the **personal background** of the teacher respondents, this could be briefly stated that as to **gender**, the majority were females with 123 or 73.65 percent and 44 or 26.35 percent were males. Regarding the **age**, 68 or 40.72 percent have an age of 46-55, followed by 36 or 21.56 percent aging 36-45, next, 26 or 15.57 percent with an age of 26-35, then 21 or 12.57 percent aging 56 and above and 16 or 9.58 percent were teachers ages 25 and below. As for the **marital status**, predominantly were married with 123 or 73.65 percent, next, single with 42 or 25.15 percent, then both widow/widower and annulled with 1 or 0.60 percent. For **combined monthly income**, 163 or 97.60 percent of them were Teachers 1, 2, and 3 received a salary that ranged from 20, 001 – 30, 000 under Salary Grades 11, 12, and 13, respectively. The remaining 4 or 2.40 percent had received 40 001 – 50, 000 a month for Master Teachers with Salary Grade 18. As to **the type of learning modality implemented in school**, 167 or 100 percent had preferred modular print for it's the only modality applicable to students living in rural areas, specifically far-flung or mountainous barangays, with no internet connectivity and with low economic status.

The **professional qualification** of the teachers could be summarily pointed out almost entirely as bachelor's degree holders with master's units with 155 or 92.82 percent, 7 or 4.19 percent were full-pledged masters, and 5 or 2.99 percent were master's degree graduates with doctoral units as to the **degree earned**. Regarding the **major and or minor field of specialization**, most of the teachers were English majors with 42 or 25.15 percent, followed by Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) with 40 or 23.95 percent, Mathematics with 32 or 19.16 percent, Physical/Biological Science with 18 or 10.78 percent, Filipino with 15 or 8.98 percent, MAPEH with 5 or 2.99 percent and Values Education majors with 4 or 2.40 percent. However, **in the length of teaching experience**, there were 75 or 44.91 percent of newly hired and newbie teachers, 35 or 20.96 percent with 6-10 years of service, 26 or 15.57 percent with 21 years and above, 25 or 14.97 percent with 11-15 years and 6 or 3.59 percent with 16-20 years of teaching experience or service in public. Regarding the **latest performance rating**, 100 percent of the teachers had a Very Satisfactory rating obtained that ranging from 3.500 – 4.499.

➤ *Levels of Manifestation of Management Practices of Administrators and Teachers as regard All Dimensions*

The Revised School-Based Management Tool 2021 was the instrument used in gathering data on the levels of management practices of School Administrators and Teachers.

Regarding **all dimensions**, both school administrators and teachers answered highly evident on the four school-based management dimensions: leadership, curriculum and instruction, learning environment, finance and resource management, and mobilization, with a weighted mean of

4.00. However, under human resource and team development, both landed on the same answer with a weighted mean of 5.00; thus, this would mean that this aspect was highly evident and well-practiced in all secondary schools within the district.

Findings showed that school-based Management was critical as it empowered the school heads to lead their teachers and students through reforms that will lead to higher learning outcomes and bring resources, including funds, down to the control of the school to spur change in line with decentralization. Further, it strengthened partnerships with communities to invest time, money, and effort in making the school a better place to learn; and integrated school management and instructional reformation for school effectiveness (D.O. 83, s. 2012).

➤ *Factors Affecting School Administrators and Teachers Management Practices in The New Normal*

External factors. Basically, these factors were the distance from home to school, mode of transportation, length of time to travel from home to school, time in going to bed, length of time to distribute the modules from one house to another, and reasons for home tutors when not around during house-to-house distribution of modules or home visits and challenges met by the Teacher during the implementation of their management practices outside school.

Distance from home to school. Generally, the respondents lived more than 1 kilometer away from school with 62 or 35.84 percent, 43 or 24.85 percent were from the neighboring municipalities, 37 or 21.39 percent were teachers who lived at the heart of the school, 16 or 9. 25 percent situated more than 500 meters but less than 1 kilometer and accessible for any transportation and others, existed in more than 2 kilometers away from school with 15 or 8. 67 percent.

Findings showed that most teachers were far from their working stations; thus, this could affect their time and school management practices. On the contrary, according to (Khan, 2007), teaching was about a vocation and not just simply a profession. Even if there were instances that teachers were late in their duty, teachers have exerted their efforts at their optimum level. It was probably due to how a teacher exercised their attempt to serve beyond the profession's call.

Mode of transportation. Results showed most of the respondents were riding a motorcycle as their means of transportation upon going to their working stations with 82 or 47.40 percent, second and third highest in the distribution were riding a tricycle or "chappy" and sent and fetched by a family vehicle with 34 or 19.65 percent and 17 or 9.83 percent respectively. Fourth on the list was riding a bus/van/jeepney/multicab because it was from the other neighboring municipality with 17 or 9.83 percent, and last will use leg power through walking or hiking with 7 or 4.05 percent.

Thus, the motorcycle was of great help upon going to working stations not late, and teachers could immediately do and accomplish things before and within the time frame.

Length of time to travel from home to school. In general, 56 or 32.37 percent, around 30 to 45 minutes travel from home to school, second, with 35 or 20.23 percent, third, with 33 or 19.08 percent, fourth, with 29 or 16.76 percent and last in the distribution with 20 or 11.56 percent.

Results exhibited that most will travel about 30 – 45 minutes from home to school since they live more than 1 kilometer away and usually ride a motorcycle going to their working stations.

It coined the idea that school head-teachers consider a distance of one kilometer to school on foot too long. If administrators and teachers walk over one kilometer to school, the outcomes would not be in the best interest of both the staff and the school because set goals and objectives may not be achieved entirely (<https://hiwriters.com.ng/product/the-effect-of-school-distance-on-students-academic-performance/>). Therefore, if the average distance to school can be shortened, school principals and teachers will have more time to dedicate to school-related work, work at home, or leisure activities and manage efforts.

The time is to go to bed. Overall, respondents will sleep at 10:00 PM, the highest in the distribution with 98 or 56.65 percent and 75 or 43.35 percent as second in the distribution that favored midnight after accomplishing home and school-related tasks.

Consequently, both had a lack of sleep, for they will have it at about 6-7 hours since they will wake up at 5:00 AM to prepare breakfast and do other errands since the average number of hours of sleep was 8 hours. Thus, this will affect work performance, productivity, quality, and working relationships. Without adequate sleep, employees will have more difficulty concentrating, learning, communicating, and managing (<https://www.forthhealthcare.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/06/sleep-deprivation-and-work-performance>).

Length of time to distribute the modules from one house to another. 117 or 67.63 percent had chosen more than 1 hour because of distant places. The second highest is 21 or 12.14 percent at approximately 45 minutes to 1 hour to transfer because home tutors were not around. The third is 14 or 18.09 percent, then 12 or 6.94 percent, and finally, 9 or 5.20 percent attested that it would be at approximately 10 minutes to transfer because houses were near each other and parents/home tutors were around.

For this, teachers' management practices in school will be hindered, for it took time to deliver modules because of students' houses situated in mountainous barangays or even far-flung areas. Sometimes, teachers will wait longer since parents are not around because they will need to earn a living. But teacher-parent relations bear increasing importance for

improving schools and managing oneself and work-related concerns as learning communities, and for students' growth through meeting their needs and expectations (Olcer & Kocer, 2015; Schussler, 2003).

➤ *Reasons for home tutors when not around during house-to-house distribution of modules or home visits.*

Mainly, 56 or 32.37 percent is the first reason parents work inside and outside the country to earn a living to sustain life and family. The second is 46 or 26.59 percent, due to time constraints between teachers and parents since parents have different ways to substantiate and raise their families. The third is 36 or 20.81 percent of the students don't have parents since it's already deceased, and 35 or 20.23 percent of parents were engaged in small or large businesses.

Teachers and school administrators had a hard time managing home and school-related work, especially in these trying times, for this external factor could affect their management practices when parents were not around during house-to-house distribution of modules or home visits. Moreover, it also breaks planned schedules. Parental involvement was essential for student development. Having parents and teachers communicate constantly helped students feel more motivated in their classes; their self-esteem and attitudes in class improved. As coined on the idea of Morin (2013), the best tip for school success is to make sure that parents, teachers, and school officials are working together as allies.

➤ *Challenges met by the Teacher during the implementation of their management practices outside school.*

The majority had responded to distant houses of students with 88 or 50.87 percent, 37 or 21.39 percent had said that students mostly lived in mountainous barangays or far-flung areas. However, 27 or 15.60 percent, where teachers don't have means of transportation to deliver modules to students, and 21 or 12.14 percent revealed that parents did not value education to their students, specifically to families belonging to the DDU sector (deprived, depressed and underserved).

In this regard, teachers could not fully implement well their management practices because of the external obstacles or barriers faced during the implementation process. As such, the allocated time will be rescheduled for some hindrances, and school administrators and teachers will adapt to changes in time for delivering and executing quality instruction to learners. To address these challenges, better time management, upgrading of teaching strategies, adapting to the unprecedented changes brought by the new trends in education, being flexible, providing alternative plans, tapping LGUs, being optimistic and patient, and equipping oneself with the appropriate skills were some of the ways on how to deal and cope with the challenges specifically in this modular distance learning modality. The teachers were facilitators of learning for student development, both as members of their community and members of their society (Martineau et al., 2020).

Internal factors. This factor primarily focused on the schedule in giving or distributing modules, reasons for the delayed distribution, time management, how they spent their vacant time and challenged the administrators and teachers met in school.

Schedule in giving or distributing modules. Mainly, 67 or 38.73 percent preferred to have it on Fridays, followed by 58 or 33.53 percent, every Monday, and the remaining 48 respondents, with 27.74 percent, will choose to distribute modules every Tuesday.

In line with these schedules on the distribution of modules, management practices of teachers will sometimes be affected by the emergency meetings conducted by the school administrators if there are important documents or paperwork that need to be compiled and submitted within that time. Moreover, teachers will modify schedules upon distribution of learning materials to attain and meet the competencies within that week. Thus, time management was also crucial because using time effectively gave the person a "choice" on tasks accomplishment at their own time and convenience (Lualhati, 2019).

Reasons for the delayed distribution. Totality, 173 or 100 percent of the school principals and teachers revealed why they were sometimes late in distributing modules because there was an occurrence of emergency meetings. It supported a study that 67% of workers said that spending too much time in meetings distracts them from doing their job (<https://www.cnbc.com/>).

Time management for them. It could be inferred that time management was a virtue to be valued and kept by one another, for 100 percent chose this option.

It coined the idea of Bilbao (2009) that time management was commonly referred to as scheduling, goal setting, prioritizing tasks, managing paperwork, and managing interruptions executed by the teachers to meet the demands of their job. Thus, this definition genuinely engraved in their minds how vital time management was explicitly on the management practices in school. These also save their time without compromising the quality of teaching and service.

How they spent their free time. Results showed that they mainly were doing school-related paper works with 155 or 89.60 percent. Others were doing classroom chores during their free time like sweeping and applying floor wax on floors, cleaning comfort rooms and wiping specks of dust on window blades, panes, and cabinets, organizing portfolios, and planting vegetables in their respective area for "Gulayan sa Paaralan", doing narrative reports on the activities they have implemented in school based on their ancillaries with 18 or 10.40 percent.

Findings showed that school administrators and teachers were occupied with schoolwork to meet the ever-growing demands of society. For school heads and teachers believed in the slogan "Para Sa Bata, Para Sa Bayan". They

have worked effortlessly to better the school and stakeholders since principals could lead school improvements through well-managed practices, building supportive and believing relationships with teachers (Sowell, 2018).

Challenges met in school. Consequently, 140 of the respondents with a percentage distribution of 80.92 percent of loaded paper works being the highest challenge or barrier met by the Teacher in school, followed by 21 or 12.14 percent on unsubmitted SLHTs of the students and 12 or 6.94 with overload subjects handled.

Based on the results, school administrators and teachers are preoccupied and overloaded with duties and responsibilities (Tancinco, 2016). Especially in these trying times, teachers experience high-stress levels and emotional exhaustion, which leads to high levels of burnout and professional attrition. As a result, management practices were affected by internal challenges or barriers that arose during implementation.

➤ *Significant Relationship Between Age, Gender, Combined Family Income, External and Internal Factors and the Levels of Manifestation as regards All Dimensions Affecting the Implementation of Management Practices of the Administrators and Teachers in the New Normal*

As reflected in Table 35, the computed p - values of **age, gender, and combined monthly income** of administrators and teachers were 0.062, 0.845, and 0.371, respectively, at a 173df of which were more significant than 0.05 level of significance. With these results, it failed to reject the null hypothesis. Further, findings exhibit that there was no significant relationship between age, gender, combined monthly income, and the external and internal factors affecting the implementation of management practices of the administrators and teachers in this new educational setup.

External and internal factors are the correlated variables affecting the implementation of management practices with a significance level of 0.05 alpha. Table 36 revealed that the p -value was 0.008. Therefore, the data implied that there was a significant relationship between these variables affecting the implementation of management practices because it was lesser than the level of significance. Thus, it rejected the null hypothesis.

Regarding the **levels of manifestations concerning all dimensions** as correlated to external and internal factors, it could summarily point out that r values were 0.002. However, the p -value on the levels of manifestation and the external factors was 0.531, and the p -value on the levels of manifestation and internal factors was 0.976. The decision, therefore, failed to reject the null hypothesis because it's much greater than the significance level of 0.05. Further interpretation stressed that there were no significant relationships between the levels of manifestation in all dimensions about the external and the internal factors.

To synthesize the significant relationships based on the specified variables that were correlated, only the external and the internal factors affect the implementation of management practices of school administrators and teachers in this new educational setup or new normal trend of teaching for which results denoted significantly.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

As stated on the results, generally that external factors and internal factors affect the implementation of management practices of school administrators and teachers, for it had a p -value of 0.008, which was lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. The external factors are the distance of home from school, mode of transportation, time of travel, time to transfer from one house to another during the distribution of modules, reasons why home tutors were not around, challenges met by the Teacher outside school, and time of sleep while internal factors are the inclusion a schedule in giving/distributing modules, reasons why late in giving/distributing modules to students or home tutors, time management, how they spent their vacant time and challenges met by the Teacher in school. Thus, the decision rejected the null hypothesis because it had a significant relationship between the latter and implementing such management practices.

On the said findings and conclusion of the study, it was now recommended to follow constantly the continuous development programs to avoid these barriers or challenges that affect the said implementation of the school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the findings, the proposed continuous development programs should be strictly followed and implemented in all five-secondary schools in Medellin District, namely, Kawit National High School, Medellin National High School, Medellin National Science, and Technology School, Curva National High School, and Almacen - Torrevillas National High School; Medellin, Cebu every school year to eliminate factors that affect their management practices in school.

Below are the salient features of the continuous development programs to be applied constantly:

First, teachers' knowledge and capabilities should be updated by letting them attend more relevant seminars and training workshops that talk mainly on Management, leadership, curriculum and instruction, learning environment, finance and resource management mobilization, governance, and most of all, human resource and team development.

Second, it could also be enlightening that there should always be LAC Sessions per month to know the issues and concerns faced by the teachers during the delivery of quality instruction and their teaching encounters.

Third, teachers should make themselves use their leisure time in doing some useful or productive works not bombarded with paper works to prepare them in the future to keep away from external and internal factors affecting their management practices and also school heads shall give them recognitions for making some innovations that aid learning despite pandemic and for doing some diligent works every quarter.

Last but not least, home visits must be given priority for they gave proper mentoring and coaching to the Teacher and the parents of the students. It must be immediately followed by feedbacking between the Teacher and the school administrator to address concerns, issues, gaps, and or problems during the implementation of the new learning delivery modality in this new educational setup.

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